

The nutritive value of forage and weed species grazed by beef cattle in Australia and the effect on livestock selectivity

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Abstract

The majority of Australian paddocks are heterogeneous (non-uniform) and hence vary in pasture biomass and quality widely at a variety of scales. Cattle are selective graziers, spending time in some areas whilst avoiding others. However, despite this, many grazing studies fail to examine the underlying pasture quality and potential influence these pasture variables have on livestock selection. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate beef cattle selectivity (time spent at a site) due to the underlying quality of pasture that had recently been sown, and non-sown pasture species along with a number of weeds.

Prior to cattle grazing, a range of pasture attributes were measured including pasture biomass and Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) along with individual plant species to determine forage quality. These were later analysed for protein, minerals, organic acids, alcohols, fibre and non-fibre carbohydrates. Paddock variables (elevation and distance to shelter, boundary fence and water) were also determined. Eleven Angus heifers were fitted with a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) collar and tracked for 58 days. Statistical analysis included pasture quality differences between species and random forest modelling to determine the main variables driving where livestock spend time.

There were significant differences across species for all pasture biomass and quality variables, except for Cu, Se and Starch. Preliminary results suggest that pasture quality variables are the major drivers of livestock selection emphasising the importance of the underlying role that pasture quality has on livestock behaviour. A repository of data for a range of pasture species including non-sown and weed species which are rarely sampled, for numerous pasture quality variables (protein, non-fibre carbohydrates, minerals etc.) is needed for improvements to be made for livestock production. By understanding the pasture quality drivers of livestock selection, producers are able to improve management practices including paddock utilisation, manipulation of pasture species and strategic rotation of paddocks.

Background

Pasture quantity and quality are the two most important attributes affecting forage preferences of grazing cattle. By understanding grazing behaviour, pasture quantity and quality interactions, strategic management decisions can be implemented such as the timely rotation of livestock. There is limited information presently available on pasture quality attributes of common sown species, and even less for non-sown and weed species. By taking into account all species present in a system and their respective quality variables, the grazing preference of cattle can be explored offering one explanation for the selective nature of grazing cattle.

Methods

This study was undertaken at The University of Sydney's Arthursleigh Farm, Big Hill NSW, Australia (34°34'7.84"S, 150° 2'15.93"E). Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was determined across the 58.8 ha paddock using a CropCircle ACS-470 system (Holland Scientific, Lincoln, NE USA). The paddock included sown species; Perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.), Phalaris (*Phalaris aquatic* L.), Cocksfoot (*Dactylis glomerata* L.), Subterranean clover (*Trifolium subterraneum* L.) and White clover (*Trifolium repens* L.). Subterranean and White clover were grouped together and are referred to as legumes.

Other species present included non-sown; Silver grass (*Vulpia* spp.) and Barley grass (*Hordeum leporinum* Link) and weed species; Shepherd's purse (*Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik) and Wireweed (*Polygonum aviculare* L.). 107 sites were selected based upon the NDVI of their location and coordinates recorded. At each site, all individual species present along with pasture biomass were sampled. Pasture biomass and quality composition including protein, non-fibre (Fructose, Glucose and Sucrose) and fibre carbohydrates (NDF, ADF, lignin, hemicellulose, cellulose, starch, non-fibrous carbohydrates and total digestible nutrients), organic acids (Malic and Citric acid), alcohols (Pinitol and myo-Inositol) and minerals (Ca, Cu, Fe, K, Mg, Mn, Na, P, S, Se, Si and Zn) were analysed for all species present. A map of every pasture variable was generated by kriging the data using VESPER (Minasny et al., 2005). The average of each pasture variable was calculated per 10 m pixel across the paddock in ArcGIS 10.2 (ESRI, 2013) and used for statistical analyses. Paddock variables (elevation, distance to water, shelter and paddock boundary) were also included in the analyses.

UNETracker II Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) collars (Trotter et al., 2010) were attached to 11 of 142 Angus heifers enabling livestock location to be tracked for the duration of the trial (58 days). Previous research by Manning et al. (2017) has found no effect of using GNSS collars on cattle behaviour. A count of the number of GPS points per 10 m pixel per heifer during the first month of the trial was used for the analyses of livestock selection.

Statistical analysis determined pasture biomass and quality differences between species using a linear mixed model, where the variable was the pasture variable of interest, pasture species being a fixed effect and no random effects. A P-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. Random forest modelling (RFM) facilitated the investigation into the effect different pasture and paddock variables have on where livestock spend time and utilise pasture resources.

Results and Discussion

All pasture biomass and quality attributes were significantly different between species ($P \leq 0.001$) except for Starch, Cu and Se ($P \geq 0.05$). For the purposes of this paper only Crude protein, biomass and non-fibre carbohydrates are focussed on in the results and discussion due to space requirements and their potential role in driving livestock selection.

Crude protein content varied from 10 %DM (Silver grass) to 18 %DM (Shepherd's purse and Wireweed), with weed species having the highest Crude protein content (Table 1). There were also significant differences in pasture biomass between species, 31 to 392 kg DM/ha, Cocksfoot and Shepherd's purse respectively (Table 1), with an average pasture biomass of 2257 kg DM/ha. Spatial paddock differences for pasture biomass and Crude protein can be seen in Figure 1 and reinforce the heterogeneous nature of paddocks typically grazed by livestock in Australian extensive production systems. Protein is one limiting requirement for ruminants (ARC, 1990) and as such is an important variable of consideration by producers. The Crude protein content of weeds was higher than other species present in this paddock. However, protein content increases with stage of maturity (Beever et al., 1989), and as all weeds were flowering may explain this higher content. Several studies exist into livestock selectivity at areas of high protein (Senft et al., 1985, Bailey, 2005, Ganskopp and Bohnert, 2009, Meisser et al., 2014). Yet, there is still a knowledge gap into how pasture quality variables drive selection, and not solely relying on research into protein selectivity.

Biomass is the most commonly measured and reported variable, playing a critical role in determining whether sufficient feed is available for grazing livestock. Sown species on average had a lower biomass (Table 1). This was expected for Cocksfoot and Phalaris (both sown species), as they are perennial species, in their first year of growth and therefore are slower growing. Shepherd's purse (weed species) recorded the highest biomass. Excluding invasive and toxic weeds, the high biomass values recorded highlights the potential underestimation of some weed species as a source of forage for grazing animals (Staver 2001).

Non-fibre carbohydrate content also significantly differed between species (Table 1), however, Glucose was the highest non-fibre carbohydrate irrespective of whether the species was sown, non-sown or a weed. Large differences in Glucose were apparent, varying from Shepherd's purse, 13 mg g⁻¹ dwt to legumes, 64 mg g⁻¹ dwt. Taste receptors enable cattle to identify different variables in pasture, including their preference for sweet substances (Albright and Arave, 1997).

The order of sweetness for non-fibre carbohydrates is Fructose, Glucose then Sucrose (Joesten et al., 2006). Silver grass and Perennial ryegrass had the highest relative sweetness (Fructose concentration). Previous research by Ciavarella et al. (2000) highlighted how water-soluble carbohydrates impacted sheep grazing selectivity, reinforcing a potential driver of cattle selectivity.

Non-sown and weed species have previously been perceived to be of little nutritional value for grazing livestock due to their perceived low quality. However, there may be little benefit in utilising limited time and labour resources to remove such species in livestock grazing systems. Obvious constraints to utilising such species is cattle preference, palatability and selection. Nevertheless, it is important to evaluate the nutritional quality of all species present in livestock grazing systems. Preliminary results into the pasture quality variables driving livestock selection reinforce that livestock are influenced by the underlying quality of pasture quality.

Table 1: Select predicted pasture biomass and quality (non-fibre carbohydrates and crude protein) concentrations across pasture species. Means with different superscripts within rows differ significantly between species ($P \leq 0.05$, based on LSD). Asterisks indicate species that were significantly different to all other species.

Category	Variable	Sown species				Non-sown species		Weed species		Species	d.f, F-statistic	P-value
		Legumes	Cocksfoot	Phalaris	Perennial ryegrass	Barley grass	Silver grass	Shepherd's Purse	Wireweed			
Biomass												
(kg DM/ha)	Biomass ¹	120a	31a	334b	148a	1	329b	392b	1	6, 42.6	<0.001	
Non-fibre carbohydrates												
(mg g ⁻¹ dwt)	Fructose	14cd	25a	28a	34b	18c	33ab	13d	15cd	7, 39.3	<0.001	
	Sucrose	1cd	5b	2cd	9a	10a	9a	3bc	0d	7, 22.7	<0.001	
	Glucose	64*	25b	30bc	48*	23a	34c	13*	29abc	7, 42.3	<0.001	
Crude Protein												
(%DM)	CP	17bc	14a	16b	14a	12a	10*	18c	18bc	7, 18.8	<0.001	

¹ Biomass also included 'Other' species at 913.1 kg DM/ha. This included any species other than the ones mentioned and included Barley grass, Wireweed and other unidentifiable species of small quantities.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of total biomass (kg DM/ha) and Crude protein (% DM) across the paddock for all species analysed

Conclusion

Dietary preference and selection by grazing livestock, feed intake and paddock utilisation has the potential to be manipulated or improved simply by knowing the pasture quality of common sown, non-sown and weed species in Australian improved paddocks. As a result, modifications can be employed to alter how livestock obtain their "preferred diet", potentially improving livestock wellbeing, production and sustainability.

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